

Green UV-spectrophotometric method for estimation of esomeprazole in injection dosage

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Abstract

A new spectroscopic method had been proposed to determine esomeprazole in pure form and pharmaceutical preparation. The method is based on the hydrolysis of esomeprazole by adding hydrochloric acid to produce a product that gives the highest absorption at a wavelength of 352 nm. In comparison, the solution of esomeprazole alone gave the highest absorption at 300 nm, indicating the suggested method gave a wave displacement. The resulting solution was soluble in water and had a molar absorptivity coefficient of 7.7×10^3 l/mol. cm. The range of estimate obeying Beer's law was from 1–40 µg/mL with a determination coefficient (R^2) of 0.9997. Some of the analytical constants related to the method of estimation were calculated, including stability, where the result was stable for an hour, and the Sandall sensitivity value was calculated and mentioned, 0.044 µg/cm². The method was also applied to estimate the compound under study in pharmaceutical preparation (tablet), and reliable analytical results were obtained. The greenness of the suggested methods was evaluated, demonstrating the minimum hazardous effect on the environment.

Keywords

esomeprazole, hydrolysis, spectrophotometry, pharmaceuticals, green chemistry

Introduction

Esomeprazole (ESM) magnesium has the property of proton pump inhibitors (PPIs), which block the production of acid by the stomach (Tripathi 2003). ESM, its chemical name ((S)-5-methoxy-2-((4-methoxy-3,5-dimethylpyridin-2-yl) methyl) sulphonyl)-1H-benzo[d]imidazole), and its structural formula (Budawari 2001) are shown in Fig. 1.

It is used to treat several diseases that affect the stomach, such as infectious erosive esophagitis and symptoms of esophageal reflux, and it is also used to treat peptic ulcers and ulcers associated with non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (Sweetman 2001).

Figure 1. The chemical structure of ESM.

ESM is used to treat a condition known as overproduction of stomach acid. It is commonly used to treat gastroesophageal reflux disease (GORD), a condition that

causes persistent acid reflux, indigestion, heartburn, and acid reflux. Bioavailability ranges from 50 to 90%, while elimination half-life is 1.1 to 1.5 hours (Perry 2016).

Several spectroscopic analytical methods had been developed for the determination of ESM present in pharmaceutical preparations and biological fluids (Raj et al. 2007; Prabu et al. 2008; Rahman et al. 2008; Gosavi et al. 2008; Jain et al. 2012; Hiwale et al. 2016; Rele et al. 2018; Manoharan et al. 2019; Cheruku et al. 2021; Kulsum et al. 2022; Abdelazim et al. 2022; Fouad et al. 2024).

In this research, a spectrophotometric method for the rapid, simple, and affordable determination of ESM in pharmaceutical preparations had been developed that could be used for regular quality control, which was the aim of the current review development. Additionally, the suggested approach to greenness was assessed, showing that it had the fewest negative environmental effects.

Materials and methods

Apparatus

The absorbance measurements and absorption spectra were obtained using a Shimadzu UV-visible 160 double-beam spectrometer equipped with glass cells measuring 1.0 centimeters. A professional benchtop pH meter, model number BP3001, was used to measure the pH of the solutions.

Chemical reagents

The materials used in this method were obtained in high purity from Fluka, BDH, and Merck.

Standard ESM solution (100 µg/mL)

Using 0.0100 g of pure ESM powder from the State Company for Drug Industries and Medical Appliances (S.D.I.), Samara-Iraq, 100 µg/mL (2.9×10^{-4} M) was made immediately by dissolving it in 10 mL of ethanol and diluting it to 100 mL with distilled water in a volumetric flask.

Hydrochloric acid solution (approximately 1 M)

Prepared by dilution of 8.7 mL of concentrated hydrochloric acid (12.1 M) to 100 mL with distilled water using a volumetric flask.

ESM injection solution (100 µg/mL)

Three injection vials were mixed together for each company separately, and then the average weight was taken of one injection, and the entire contents of the injection (**Nexium Esoblok**) containing 40 mg of the active substance ESM were dissolved in distilled water; then the volume was completed to 100 mL using a volumetric flask, after which the concentration was diluted to the equivalent of 100 µg/mL with distilled water.

The general principle of the procedure

The general principle of the proposed method involved the decomposition of ESM by adding 1 mL of dilute hydrochloric acid (1 M) to 1 mL of 100 µg of ESM in a final volume of 10 mL in a volumetric flask. It was observed that when the acid was added, the reaction gave the highest absorption at the maximum wavelength of 352 nm, while ESM gave its highest absorption at the maximum wavelength of 300 nm, so there was a shift of the maximum wavelength, as was clear in the following equation.

The wavelength for ESM in the UV spectrum

A 10 mL volumetric flask contained 1 mL of ESM standard stock solution (100 µg/mL), which was then diluted with distilled water to a mark. A UV (200–400 nm) scan was performed on the resultant solution. ESM displayed the highest absorption at 300 nm in the spectrum.

Results and discussion

Optimum conditions for the reaction

Several trials were carried out using this technique, utilizing 100 µg of ESM in a final volume of 10 mL to investigate and select the ideal parameters for the reaction that produces the highest absorbency.

Effect of acid solution

Several acid solutions, including hydrochloric acid, sulfuric acid, nitric acid, acetic acid, and phosphoric acid, at a concentration of 1M for each, were studied by adding 2 mL of each acid and recording the absorbance value of the resulting solution. The results shown in Table 1 showed that 1M HCl gave the best absorbance value (0.226), so it was adopted.

Table 1. Effect of various types of acid solutions on absorbance.

Acid (2 mL, 1M)	Absorbance
HCl	0.226
H ₂ SO ₄	0.220
HNO ₃	0.078
CH ₃ COOH	0.191
H ₃ PO ₄	0.219

The effect of volume hydrochloric acid

In order to obtain the best absorption value, the effect of several different volumes of hydrochloric acid (0.25–3 mL) at 1M on the absorption value of the final product was studied. It was observed that by adding 2 mL of acid, the highest absorbance value was obtained, as shown in Fig. 2, which was adopted in subsequent experiments.

Figure 2. Effect of HCl volume.

The duration of development and stability

The influence of time on the stability of the resultant at 352 nm was examined at room temperature and under pre-established experimental conditions using two different concentrations of 100 and 200 μg of ESM. The data in Fig. 3 demonstrate that the absorbance values of the resulting remained almost consistent for sixty minutes.

Figure 3. Effect of time on absorbance.

Absorption spectra

The final absorption spectra of the product were obtained under the optimum procedure conditions by applying the proposed method to 100 μg of ESM in a 10 mL volumetric flask. Fig. 4 shows the final spectrum of the method, where the resulting spectrum gave the highest absorbance value (0.221) at 352 nm.

Recommended procedure and calibration curve

In a series of 10 mL volumetric increasing volumes of 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ ESM working solution ranging from 0.1 to 4 mL were added, followed by 2 mL of 1 M hydrochloric acid solution, with well shaking of the contents, and then the flasks were filled up to the mark with distilled water. The ab-

Figure 4. Absorption spectra of (A) 10 μg ESM/mL vs. D.W. and (B) ESM vs. blank (D.W.+HCl).

sorbance values of the products formed were taken against their blank solutions at 352 nm and recorded. A standard curve of the procedure was plotted depending on the curve; the linearity between the absorbance values and the ESM concentration was in the range of 1–40 μg of ESM/mL, as shown in Fig. 5. The apparent molar absorbance was 7.737×10^3 L/mol.cm, and Sandall sensitivity was 0.0446 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$.

Figure 5. The calibration curve for ESM determination.

Accuracy and precision

The ESM was determined using three quantities of its working solution (50, 100, and 250 $\mu\text{g}/10$ mL) and repeating the process five times for each concentration in order to identify the accuracy and precision of the proposed procedure. The results of this study recorded in Table 2 confirmed that the proposed method had acceptable accuracy and precision.

Table 2. Accuracy and precision.

Present amount of ESM $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$	Found amount of ESM $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$	Recovery %*	Relative error, %	Relative standard deviation, %
5.00	4.991	99.82	-0.18	3.45
10.0	9.890	98.90	-1.1	2.55
25.0	25.075	100.30	0.03	2.73

*Average of five determinations.

Table 3. Determination of ESM in pharmaceutical preparations.

Pharmaceuticals	ESM Present ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	ESM Found ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Recovery %*	Relative error %	RSD%	**t exp.
Nexium 40 mg	5.0	1.086	2.4	-1.20	98.80	4.94
ESM/Injection	10.0	0.949	1.59	-0.10	99.90	9.99
AstraZeneca/UK	25.0	1.909	2.75	-2.28	97.72	24.43
Esoblok 40 mg	50	0.781	2.95	-1.20	98.80	49.4
ESM/Injection	100	1.186	1.52	0.80	100.80	100.8
Turkey	250	0.234	0.29	-0.04	99.96	249.9

*Average of four determinations

**texp. value was calculated using:

$$\pm t = (\bar{X} - M) + \sqrt{N/S.D}$$

Application of the method

ESM was successfully analyzed in pharmaceuticals (injectable) using the present method. The results summarized in Table 3 showed acceptable accuracy of the proposed.

Table 3 results show that the experimental “t-test” values are less than the theoretical “t-test” value in table (3.18) at a (95)% confidence level for four measured samples. The value indicated that there are no significant differences between the two values (calculated and theoretical) (Christian et al. 2014).

Quantification

The analytical values obtained using this method are included in this study's Table 4, and based on the information given in this table, the proposed method is considered to have good sensitivity and accuracy.

Table 4. Optical characteristics and statistical data for the proposed method.

Parameter	Data
Limits of Beer's law, $\mu\text{g/mL}$	1–40
λ_{max} , nm	352
ϵ , L/mol.cm	7.7×10^3
Range of recovery*, %	97.72–100.80
Relative error range*, %	-2.28–0.8
RSD, %	Not more than 2.95
Sandell sensitivity, $\mu\text{g/cm}^2$	0.044
Determination coefficient (R^2)	0.9997
Slope (a) [†]	0.0224
Intercept (b) [†]	0.0027

Regression equation $X = aY + b$, where Y is [ESM] in $\mu\text{g/mL}$

*Average of five determinations

Evaluation of the suggested procedure

The standard addition method was successfully performed (Harris 2016) using two different concentrations (5 & 8) of working solution for each pharmaceutical preparation (Nexium injection and Esoblok injection), and the results shown in Fig. 6 and Table 5 demonstrated that the proposed method had good selectivity for the determination of ESM in pharmaceutical preparations.

Figure 6. Standard addition curves for estimation of ESM in pharmaceutical preparations.**Table 5.** The results of standard addition methods for analysis of ESM.

Pharmaceuticals	Present ESM ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Measured ESM ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Recovery (%)
Nexium 40 mg	5	4.97	99.40
ESM/Injection	8	8.086	101.07
AstraZeneca/UK			
Esoblok 40 mg	5	5.01	100.20
ESM/Injection	8	8.16	102.00
Turkey			

Green analytical chemistry

Green analytical chemistry aimed to make analytical processes safer for people and the environment. Many factors were considered when evaluating the greenness of an analytical approach, including the quantity and toxicity of re-

agents, waste produced, energy requirements, the number of procedural steps, downsizing, and automation. Using greenness evaluation criteria calls for certain instruments. The Analytical Greenness calculator was presented, a thorough, adaptable, and uncomplicated evaluation method that yielded an understandable and instructive outcome. The evaluation criteria were converted into a single 0–1 scale using the 12 principles of green analytical chemistry (SIGNIFICANCE). The SIGNIFICANCE principles were used to compute the final score. The outcome was a pictogram that showed the analytical procedure's performance and final score. According to the data of the proposed method, no organic reagent or any toxic chemicals were used, so this proposed method could be considered one of the environmentally friendly methods. Therefore, using the Analytical Greenness-AGREE (Pereira et al. 2020).

The method was evaluated by entering the information that was deduced from the research into 12 variables in the AGREE system. The result obtained was 0.86, and this result indicates that the method can be described as environmentally friendly (Fig. 7).

Analytical Greenness report sheet

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Criteria	Score	Weight
1. Direct analytical techniques should be applied to avoid sample treatment.	0.85	2
2. Minimal sample size and minimal number of samples are goals.	0.8	2
3. If possible, measurements should be performed in situ.	0.8	2
4. Integration of analytical processes and operations saves energy and reduces the use of reagents.	0.8	2
5. Automated and miniaturized methods should be selected.	0.75	2
6. Derivatization should be avoided.	0.8	2
7. Generation of a large volume of analytical waste should be avoided, and proper management of analytical waste should be provided.	0.39	2
8. Multi-analyte or multi-parameter methods are preferred versus methods using one analyte at a time.	0.55	2
9. The use of energy should be minimized.	0.8	2
10. Reagents obtained from renewable sources should be preferred.	0.8	2
11. Toxic reagents should be eliminated or replaced.	0.8	2
12. The operator's safety should be increased.	0.8	2

Figure 7. Analytical Greenness report sheet.

Compare the proposed method with other UV methods

The values of the spectroscopic analytical variables of the proposed method for the determination of ESM were compared with the same variables of spectroscopic methods from previous literature, and the results were recorded in Table 6.

Table 6. Comparison of some analytical spectroscopic variables and application of the proposed method with other spectrophotometric methods.

Parameter	Present method	Literature method [5]	Literature method [6]
Type of reaction	UV	UV	UV
Reagent	(1M) HCl	–	Methanol
λ_{\max} (nm)	352	305	301
Medium of reaction	–	Basic	–
Temperature (°C)	At room temperature	At room temperature	At room temperature
Beer's law range ($\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$)	1–40	5–25	30–70
Correlation coefficient (R^2)	0.9997	0.9963	0.9962
Molar absorptivity ($\text{L}/\text{mol}\cdot\text{cm}$)	7.7×10^3	1.40×10^4	1.72×10^3
RSD (%)	Not more than 2.95	Less than 2	0.8
Recovery (%)	97.72–100.80	97.46–102.7%	99.56–102.5
Relative error (%)	-2.28–0.8	–	–
Sandell sensitivity ($\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$)	0.044	0.024	0.2
Application of the method	Injection	Tablets	Solid dosage form
The green index	0.84	–	–

The results in the above table showed that our results were equally significant to the outcomes of the two methods used for comparison, and the present method was considered a friend to the environment according to Analytical Greenness-AGREE.

Conclusion

The present research included an accurate, low-cost, and low-complexity UV-spectrophotometric development method for assaying ESM in pharmaceutical dosage (injection) at room temperature without the need for separation processes. The results of this technique were accurate and specific enough to detect ESM in pharmaceutical preparations. Greenness evaluation of the described models was done using the analytical eco-scale, the green analytical procedure index, and the AGREE evaluation method. The results showed that the described models complied with and met the environmental friendliness characteristics in terms of the official green metric values.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.